

Supplementary file 6. Gene overlap with LOH blocks and positive functional enrichment results obtained.

1. Distribution of the frequency of gene homozygosity per strain in each of the hybrid clades.

2. Positive results of the GO enrichment analysis between genes covered in < 50% of their length by LOH blocks (heterozygous) and genes covered in \geq 50% of their length by LOH blocks (homozygous), according to the mean of all *C. metapsilosis* strains, and using a minimum LOH block size of 100bp.

Genes: 3716

Gos: 9893

Finished execution successfully.

Execution time: 1 sec.

OVER REPRESENTED TERMS

Term category: cellular_component

#overlist	term	term level	adj.pvalue	term name
1	GO:0005618	1	4.101590e-07	cell wall
1	GO:0009277	1	4.101590e-07	fungus-type cell wall
1	GO:0009986	1	3.707860e-06	cell surface
1	GO:0030312	1	4.101590e-07	external encapsulating structure

3. Positive results of the GO enrichment analysis between genes covered in < 50% of their length by LOH blocks (heterozygous) and genes covered in \geq 50% of their length by LOH blocks (homozygous), according to the median of all *C. metapsilosis* strains, and using a minimum LOH block size of 100bp.

Genes: 3716

Gos: 9893

Finished execution successfully.

Execution time: 2 sec.

OVER REPRESENTED TERMS

Term category: cellular_component

#overlist	term	term level	adj.pvalue	term name
1	GO:0005618	1	1.249970e-04	cell wall
1	GO:0009277	1	1.249970e-04	fungus-type cell wall
1	GO:0009986	1	4.460300e-04	cell surface
1	GO:0030312	1	1.249970e-04	external encapsulating structure